

Trends, Composition And Quality Of Non-Farm Employment In Rural Punjab

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Abstract

The paper explores employment trends in Punjab since 2004-05 based on the study of rounds of NSS and PLFS unit-level data. There has been a significant shift in Punjab's rural economy, marked by a considerable decline in the percentage of rural workers involved in agriculture activities, while the number of those engaged in non-farm activities within the rural areas has experienced a substantial increase since 2004-05. However, only service sector jobs have produced better results among the rural non-farm sectors. The industrial manufacturing and non-manufacturing industries have a long way to go to employ the rural population of Punjab profitably. Strangely, the service sector, which has been the primary driver of employment in rural Punjab, has continuously seen a rise in informality and unorganised segments. The number of workers engaged in micro and small enterprises with no written job contract, paid leaves and job security is on the rise post-2012.

Keywords

Agriculture, Rural workforce, Rural Non-Farm Employment, Rural Punjab.

Introduction

Punjab staged a spectacular performance in food grain production from the early 1960s to the middle of the 1980s. With the introduction of Green Revolution technologies in the mid-1960s, Punjab showed its star performance in raising agricultural production and productivity, saving the country from acute food shortages and heavy dependence on food imports. Punjab's role in securing the much-needed food security in the country at that time, thus, cannot be undermined. However, this rosy image of Punjab did not last long, and it was entirely dismantled by the ugly head of the crisis that followed the state's agricultural success. Following the mid-1980s, the positive outcomes of the Green Revolution began to recede.

Punjab's agriculture sector exhibited remarkable annual growth of 5.7 per cent during the period spanning from 1971-72 to 1985-86. However, the Green Revolution in Punjab has now completed its full cycle, from high growth to stagnation to crises. Between 1986-87 to 2004-05, the agricultural growth in Punjab slowed down to 3 per cent annually and further declined to a mere 1.9 per cent in the more recent period of 2005-06 to 2018-19 (Gulati et al., 2021). In the period of 2004-05 to 2011-12, the contribution of agriculture and related activities to Punjab's Gross State Value Added (GSVA) decreased from 32.67 per cent to 30.81 per cent. Subsequently, it experienced a further decline to 25.52 per cent as per estimates of 2017-18 (Economic and Statistical Organisation of Punjab, 2017-18).

Stagnant agricultural production and crop yields, a growing number of farmer suicides driven by debt, deteriorating land and water resources, low-profit margins and the prevalence of wheat-paddy monoculture, etc., have collectively led Punjab into a deep economic crisis (Sidhu, 2002). These problems that farmers in the agricultural sector face have led them to look for alternatives for their livelihood other than agriculture. Moreover, Punjab's urban industrial sector still needs to improve, mainly because the state has no local benefits in terms of material supply and markets for industrial products (Ohno et al., 2019). Therefore, rural Punjab has been witnessing diversification in economic activity, with a growing emphasis on the non-farm sectors, and the pattern is closely aligned with the all-India picture. In this context, where agriculture is getting highly mechanised to meet the demands of intensive farming and the state's industrial sector is also not sufficiently developed to create adequate employment opportunities for the surplus workforce, the

growth of the non-farm sector in Punjab becomes imperative to sustain the ongoing process of structural transformation.

The primary focus of this paper is to examine the post-2005 trends and patterns within Punjab's rural non-farm sector, with a particular focus on the sectoral distribution of non-farm workers. The paper also delves into the indicators related to the quality of non-farm employment. Accordingly, the paper is structured as follows: Section II reviews previous literature. Section III outlines the data sources and methodology used in this study. Section IV analyses the employment trends and patterns of non-farm employment in India and Punjab, with a special focus on sectoral disaggregation of the rural non-farm workforce in Punjab. Section V highlights the sub-sectors that have influenced the growth or decline of non-farm employment in Punjab. Section VI assesses the quality of employment generated in the non-farm sectors. Finally, Section VII presents the paper's conclusion.

Review of Literature

Kumar et al. (2011) examined the trends and patterns of rural diversification in India and across central Indian states. They utilised household-level data from NSSO spanning from 1983 to 2009-10. The analysis revealed that the proportion of the rural workforce engaged in the non-farm sector at the national level increased from one-fifth in 1983 to one-third in 2009-10. The study suggested implementing a well-designed technical program based on the local conditions of a specific area, which can equip individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge to increase the likelihood of engaging in non-farm activities.

Pavithra and Vatta (2013) examined the role of the non-farm sector in promoting rural livelihoods for landless and marginal land households in Punjab, India. The study indicated that households with productive assets were to diversify into more productive non-farm activities. In contrast, landless and marginal farmers had to rely on non-remunerative activities due to low education levels, lack of skills, and limited capital.

Chand and Srivastava (2014) analysed the changes in the rural workforce in India over 16 years, from 1993-94 to 2009-10. They observed that the increase in the rural workforce was primarily driven by the growth in the male labour force, while the share of the female workforce declined during this period. The paper also discussed the process of rural diversification from agriculture to non-farm sector, which was influenced by various factors such as patterns of economic growth, wage rate and worker productivity across sectors, education, government programmes and socio-cultural factors.

Singh and Bhogal (2014) highlighted the ongoing process of depeasantisation in Punjab since 1991. The study conducted in selected villages of Punjab revealed that since 1991, 14.39 per cent of farmers had left farming. The study identified various factors contributing to farmers leaving agriculture, including the unprofitable nature of agriculture, high land rent, lack of available family labour, emigration, and high debt burden.

Saha and Verick (2016) analysed the role of agriculture in rural diversification across various states in rural India. They found that the construction industry emerged as the most significant contributor to non-farm employment, with its contribution rising significantly from 14.4 per cent in 1993-94 to 30.1 per cent in 2011-12.

Kumar and Shergill (2017) analysed the dynamics of rural non-farm employment (RNFE) in 15 central states of India by utilising panel data analysis covering 1972 to 2010. The analysis revealed that the factors influencing the growth of RNFE in the selected states exhibited significant gender differences. Factors like agricultural productivity and rural poverty have had a positive impact on the prevalence of RNFE, particularly for female workers.

Mehrotra and Parida (2019) observed that the process of structural transformation in the Indian economy, which had been advancing steadily since 2004-05, faced a setback starting in 2012 primarily due to a decline in employment opportunities within the agriculture and manufacturing sectors, along with sluggish growth in construction jobs. To tackle the challenges of agrarian transformation, they suggested having a holistic approach by improving rural wages, promoting industrial development and addressing skill-related issues.

Kaur and Kumar (2022) conducted a study in the western plains zone of Punjab, using both primary and secondary data sources, to analyse the extent and pattern of rural non-farm employment among Scheduled Caste (SC) respondents. The study showed that the individuals engaged in farm and non-farm activities earned twice that of those involved in farm activities.

Das and Mahanta (2023) conducted a study on rural India utilising secondary data from employment and unemployment rounds of NSSO, which included data from 61st round (2004-05), 66th round (2009-10) and 68th round (2011-12). The study's findings revealed that educated females from land-owning households had a lower likelihood of diversifying their occupations. Additionally, the study highlighted that females from SC/ST households tended to diversify more in low-return non-farm activities like manufacturing and construction. At the same time, males were more inclined to join the services sector.

Methodology

The paper's findings are drawn from the analysis of unit-level data from the employment and unemployment rounds of the NSSO, specifically the 61st round (2004–05), 68th round (2011–12), and the Periodic Labour Force Survey (PLFS) conducted in 2017–18. To estimate the figures and percentages, both usual principal and subsidiary status (UPSS) have been considered. The study focuses on individuals aged 15-59 years who are involved in the rural non-farm sector. The absolute employment figures have been determined by extrapolating the 2001 and 2011 census population figures for the years corresponding to the NSS and PLFS rounds and drawing the respective estimates from the extrapolated figures. Sector-wise estimates have been prepared per NIC-2008 estimates for comparison across three-time frames.

Analysis

IV. Employment Trends in India and Punjab

The changing employment structure at the broader industry level in both Punjab and the country as a whole is shown in Table 1. In Punjab, the share of the workforce involved in the agriculture sector declined significantly from about 50 per cent in 2004-05 to 26 per cent in 2017-18, compared to 59 per cent to 44 per cent in the country during the same period. On the other hand, the share of Punjab's manufacturing and non-manufacturing sectors witnessed continuous growth during the reference years. The service sector in Punjab experienced the most significant increase, with its share rising from 28 to 41 per cent in Punjab compared to 23 to 31 per cent in the country during 2004-05 and 2017-18, respectively. These findings indicate that Punjab has experienced a more significant shift of the workforce towards non-farm sectors, primarily driven by a more rapid decline in the share of the agriculture sector compared to the national level.

Table 1: Distribution of workforce at sectoral level in Punjab and India, 2005-18 (in per cent)

Sectors	Punjab			India		
	2004-05	2011-12	2017-18	2004-05	2011-12	2017-18
Agriculture	49.9	36.5	26.0	58.5	48.9	44.1
Manufacturing	12.7	16.8	18.9	11.7	12.7	12.1
Non-Manufacturing	9.3	14.7	14.2	6.4	11.6	12.7
Services	28.1	32.0	40.9	23.4	26.8	31.1
Total Employment	100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Author's calculation from NSS and PLFS unit-level data

Sectoral Disaggregation of Rural Workforce in Punjab

This sub-section attempts to understand the pattern of rural non-farm employment in Punjab at aggregate and disaggregate levels. In terms of both population and employment share, Punjab continues to be mainly a rural economy since about 62 per cent of Punjab's population (Census, 2011) and 60 per cent of the state's workforce belong to rural areas (PLFS, 2017-18). In Punjab, rural workers' reliance on agriculture fell by half from around 52 lakh workers in 2004-05 to 25 lakh workers in 2017-18 (see Table 2). The departure of around 27 lakh rural workers from the state's agricultural sector in just 14 years (2005-2018) is worrisome. Indeed, one of the reasons for analysing Punjab's rural non-farm sector was the massive exit of rural workers from the agriculture sector.

The sector-wise disaggregation reveals substantial shifts in the contribution of rural folks to Punjab's economy. Total cultivators in the agriculture sector declined by more than half from 36 lakh in 2004-05 to 19 lakh in 2017-18 (see Table 2), and the agricultural labourers also declined by nine percentage points in the same period. In 2017-18, the sectoral composition of RNFE depicted that the service sector accounted for the largest share of non-farm employment among both rural males and females, followed by non-manufacturing (notably construction) and manufacturing sectors.

Table 2 also shows that employment grew in Punjab's rural manufacturing sector from 5.7 lakh in 2004-05 to 8.1 lakh in 2011-12. However, in 2017-18, it declined by 1 lakh to 7.1 lakh. The same is valid for non-manufacturing (mainly construction) jobs. In the non-manufacturing sector of rural Punjab, the absolute number of workers increased from 7.5 lakh in 2004-05 to 12.6 lakh in 2011-12 and then declined to 10.7 lakh in 2017-18. Only

the service sector among the rural non-farm sectors continuously generated jobs in rural Punjab.

Although the service sector showed great success in creating jobs between 2011-12 and 2017-18, declining employment in the manufacturing and construction sectors failed to compensate for the enormous decline in agricultural employment during this period. Therefore, rural employment in Punjab generally declined between 2011-12 and 2017-18.

Table 2: Gender-wise distribution of rural workforce at sectoral level in Punjab, 2005-18 (in lakh)

Particulars	Male			Female			Persons		
	2004-05	2011-12	2017-18	2004-05	2011-12	2017-18	2004-05	2011-12	2017-18
1. Agriculture	27.6	22.9	21.3	24.3	15.2	3.6	51.9	38.1	25.0
1.1 Cultivators	17.5	15.0	16.2	14.7	8.0	2.3	36.2	23.6	19.0
1.2 Agricultural labourer	10.1	8.0	5.1	9.6	7.2	1.3	15.7	14.5	6.0
2. Non-farm	22.8	29.7	31.1	2.8	5.0	5.3	25.6	34.6	36.4
2.1 Manufacturing	4.7	6.0	5.6	1.0	2.2	1.5	5.7	8.1	7.1
2.2 Non- Manufacturing	7.5	12.4	10.2	0.0	0.2	0.5	7.5	12.6	10.7
2.3 Services	10.6	11.3	15.3	1.8	2.6	3.3	12.4	13.9	18.5
Total Rural Workforce	50.4	52.6	52.4	27.1	20.2	8.9	77.5	72.7	61.4

Source: Author's calculation from NSS and PLFS unit-level data

Gender Aspects of Rural Non-Farm Employment in Punjab

In recent decades, the gender aspect of rural employment has gained significant importance, primarily due to the deteriorating status of females in society (Jha, 2006). A growing number of rural women are seeking higher education (education effect), the household incomes are rising, and consequently, more and more women are attending to domestic duties due to the 'income effect'. However, lower female participation in rural employment can be attributed to factors such as limited employment opportunities for women and other socio-cultural factors (Neff et al., 2012).

After 2004-05, a quantum change in the male and female rural workforce towards the non-farm sector was observed in Punjab. Table 2 shows that the number of rural male workers in non-farm sectors is more than their female counterparts. Because of mechanisation and other technological advancements, females were forced out of the agriculture sector as the traditional works of winnowing, threshing, etc., are increasingly being done by machines. The period from 2004-05 to 2017-2018 has witnessed the 'defeminisation of agriculture' with about half of the women leaving the agricultural sector and their number declining from 24.3 lakh in 2004-05 to just 3.6 lakh in 2017-18. However, we see that the female rural workforce that left the agriculture sector was not absorbed in non-farm, since the number of females engaged in the non-farm sector has slightly increased from 2.8 lakh in 2004-05 to 5.3 lakh in 2017-18. Thus, we can draw inferences from the data that it is mainly the decline in rural employment, which is further caused mainly by a decline in the rural female workforce and the slow growth of rural manufacturing and construction jobs, which led to the decline in total employment in Punjab after 2012.

V. Sub-Sectors of Non-Farm Sector Driving Employment Growth in Rural Punjab, 2005-2018

In the previous sections, we observed a significant reduction in the share of the agriculture sector in Punjab's total employment and the corresponding rise in the share of non-farm sectors post-2005 period. However, when we examine the employment trends in rural Punjab, it becomes evident that a substantial proportion of the rural workforce is still employed in the agricultural sector (25 lakh in 2017-18). Only service sector jobs have produced better results among the rural non-farm sectors. The industrial manufacturing and non-manufacturing industries have a long way to go to employ the rural population of Punjab profitably. In this particular segment, an attempt is made to find out the sub-sectors within the manufacturing, non-manufacturing, and service sectors that have played a role in the growth and decline of rural non-farm employment in Punjab.

Rural Manufacturing Employment

To relieve the burden on agriculture, the growth and advancement of the industrial sector hold significant importance. In Punjab, it is the unorganised sector that has been instrumental in driving the growth of non-farm employment. The unorganised segment of Punjab's manufacturing industry comprises labour-intensive agro-based industries that require comparatively fewer skills and can employ large numbers of rural workforce. Table 3 reveals that the manufacturing industry of Punjab consists of both labour-intensive and capital-intensive sub-sectors. Between 2004-05 and 2011-12, the labour-intensive subsectors of Punjab's rural manufacturing industry contributed significantly to the growth of jobs in this sector. Roughly 2.5 lakh jobs were created in the rural manufacturing industry in Punjab over the eight years 2004-05 to 2011-12. Nevertheless, these sub-sectors suffered a decrease in jobs post-2012.

Within the manufacturing sector, the sub-sectors that generate employment include food and beverages, textiles and wearing apparel, basic metals and non-metallic products, furniture and sports goods industries. However, it is important to note that most of these sectors witnessed stagnation or a decline in employment between 2004-05 and 2017-18. In Punjab, the decline of the agro-based industries producing wood, leather, rubber products, textiles, etc., is alarming, as there is still constant strain on the state to raise income and jobs beyond agriculture, where development has almost stagnated.

The need for more expertise and skilled knowledge is the biggest challenge for rural workers entering capital-intensive manufacturing sub-sectors (Chand et al., 2017). For agriculture-displaced labourers to find employment in the rural manufacturing sector, there is a need to take pragmatic policy measures to develop labour-intensive subsectors of the manufacturing industry in Punjab, as these sectors do not demand much skill and professionalism. Strengthening the capital-intensive subsectors is equally essential to accommodate the vast youth population of Punjab, who have stayed out of work for a long time to attain education and training.